

To Study the Burden of Anemia in Non-Communicable Diseases in a Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia is a prevalent condition worldwide, significantly impacting patients with non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as diabetes, hypertension, chronic kidney disease (CKD), and cardiovascular diseases. Despite its high prevalence and adverse outcomes, anemia in NCDs often remains underdiagnosed and undertreated, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Aim: This study aimed to assess the prevalence of anemia among patients with NCDs attending a tertiary care center in India, identifying demographic and clinical factors associated with anemia to inform targeted interventions.

Methods: A total of 120 patients diagnosed with NCDs were included. Data were collected on demographic details, type and duration of NCD, and hemoglobin levels. Anemia was defined according to World Health Organization (WHO) criteria. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with chi-square tests used to assess associations between variables.

Results: The overall prevalence of anemia among the study participants was 52.5%. Anemia was more prevalent among females (65.4%), older adults (especially those >60 years, 70.0%), and patients with CKD (66.7%). Anemia prevalence increased with the duration of NCD, with 66.0% of patients with a disease duration of over 5 years being anemic. Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between anemia and gender ($p=0.015$), age ($p=0.026$), type of NCD ($p=0.003$), and duration of NCD ($p<0.001$).

Conclusion: The study found a high prevalence of anemia among patients with NCDs, particularly among females, older adults, and those with chronic kidney disease or long-standing NCDs. These findings underscore the need for routine anemia screening and management in patients with NCDs to improve clinical outcomes.

Recommendations: Routine screening for anemia should be integrated into the management protocols for patients with NCDs, especially for those at higher risk, such as older adults and patients with chronic kidney disease. Early intervention strategies, including nutritional supplementation and tailored treatment plans, should be implemented to address this comorbidity effectively.

Keywords: Anemia, Non-communicable diseases, Prevalence, Chronic kidney disease, Tertiary care center

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Introduction

Anaemia is a common public health problem characterised by a drop in haemoglobin concentration, red blood cell count, or both, resulting in poor oxygen delivery to tissues. Globally, anaemia affects an estimated 1.74 billion individuals, with the highest impact in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) [1]. Anaemia is commonly attributed to nutritional inadequacies, infectious infections, and hereditary abnormalities; nevertheless, it is becoming recognised as a substantial comorbidity in patients with (NCDs), particularly in ageing populations [2]. Non communicable diseases, such as cardiovascular disease, diabetes, (CKD), and chronic respiratory

diseases, are among the main causes of morbidity and mortality around the world. (WHO) says that NCDs account for approximately 71% of all global fatalities, with the burden disproportionately affecting low- and middle-income [3]. Anaemia is a common public health problem characterised by a drop in haemoglobin concentration, red blood cell count, or both, resulting in poor oxygen delivery to tissues. Worldwide, anaemia affects an estimated 1.74 billion individuals, with the highest As the frequency of NCDs rises, particularly in countries undergoing epidemiological change, the link between these chronic illnesses and anaemia has become a major concern.

Anaemia in the context of NCDs is complex, involving chronic inflammation, decreased renal function, dietary inadequacies, and the side effects of long-term drug usage [4]. Anaemia in CKD patients is generally caused by decreased erythropoietin synthesis, a hormone necessary for red blood cell development, combined with iron shortage and chronic inflammation [5]. Anaemia in diabetes mellitus can be caused by renal impairment, chronic inflammation, and autonomic neuropathy, all of which impede erythropoietin secretion [6]. Cardiovascular disorders, particularly heart failure, are associated with anaemia, with reasons including hemo dilution, iron deficiency, and impaired renal perfusion [7].

Anaemia in NCD patients is linked to poorer clinical outcomes, such as greater hospitalisation, lower quality of life, and higher mortality rates [8]. Despite its major impact, anaemia in NCD patients is frequently underdiagnosed and undertreated, especially in resource-limited settings. Understanding the prevalence and causes of anaemia in this population is critical for creating tailored therapies that enhance patient outcomes. This study aimed to assess the prevalence of anemia among patients with NCDs attending a tertiary care center in India, identifying demographic and clinical factors associated with anemia to inform targeted interventions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a hospital-based cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Patna Medical College and Hospital (PMCH), a tertiary care center in Patna, Bihar, India conducted over a period of one year, from January 2018 to January 2019.

Participants: A total of 120 patients diagnosed with (NCDs) were included in the study. These patients were recruited from various outpatient and inpatient departments of PMCH.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with at least one non-communicable disease (e.g., diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, chronic kidney disease).
- Patients willing to provide informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with a known history of hematological disorders (other than anemia).
- Pregnant women or women in the postpartum period.
- Patients receiving treatment for anemia at the time of study enrollment.
- Patients with acute infections or chronic inflammatory diseases that could confound the results.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, patients were randomly selected from the eligible pool of NCD patients attending the outpatient and inpatient departments during the study period. Efforts were made to include a diverse group of patients with different types of NCDs to ensure representativeness.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured proforma, which included demographic details, clinical history, and laboratory investigations. Hemoglobin levels were measured using an automated hematology analyzer, and anemia was defined according to the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria (Hb < 13 g/dL in men and Hb < 12 g/dL in women).

Procedure

Eligible participants were identified based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. After obtaining informed consent, participants underwent a detailed clinical examination and laboratory investigations. Data on demographic variables, type and duration of NCD, and hemoglobin levels were recorded.

Statistical Analysis: The data were input and analysed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarise the information. Continuous variables were displayed as means and standard deviations, whilst categorical variables were displayed as frequencies and percentages. The prevalence of anaemia was determined for the total cohort and stratified according to age, gender, and type of NCD. Categorical variables were analysed using chi-square tests, with a p-value <0.05 indicating statistical significance.

Results

A total of 120 patients diagnosed with (NCDs) were included in the study.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants (N = 120)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	68	56.7%
Female	52	43.3%
Age Group (years)		
18-30	10	8.3%
31-45	30	25.0%
46-60	50	41.7%
>60	30	25.0%
Type of NCD		
Hypertension	40	33.3%
Diabetes Mellitus	35	29.2%
Cardiovascular Diseases	20	16.7%
Chronic Kidney Disease	15	12.5%
Chronic Respiratory Diseases	10	8.3%
Duration of NCD (years)		
< 1 year	20	16.7%
1-5 years	50	41.7%
> 5 years	50	41.7%

Prevalence of Anemia: The overall prevalence of anemia among the study participants was 52.5% (63 out of 120). The prevalence of anemia was higher among females (65.4%) compared to males (42.6%). Table 2 shows the distribution of anemia across different demographic and clinical variables.

Table 2: Prevalence of Anemia by Demographic and Clinical Variables

Variable	Anemia Present (n=63)	Anemia Absent (n=57)	p-value
Gender			
Male	29 (42.6%)	39 (57.4%)	0.015
Female	34 (65.4%)	18 (34.6%)	
Age Group (years)			
18-30	4 (40.0%)	6 (60.0%)	0.026
31-45	10 (33.3%)	20 (66.7%)	
46-60	28 (56.0%)	22 (44.0%)	
>60	21 (70.0%)	9 (30.0%)	
Type of NCD			
Hypertension	18 (45.0%)	22 (55.0%)	0.003
Diabetes Mellitus	20 (57.1%)	15 (42.9%)	
Cardiovascular Diseases	12 (60.0%)	8 (40.0%)	
Chronic Kidney Disease	10 (66.7%)	5 (33.3%)	
Chronic Respiratory Diseases	3 (30.0%)	7 (70.0%)	
Duration of NCD (years)			
< 1 year	5 (25.0%)	15 (75.0%)	<0.001
1-5 years	25 (50.0%)	25 (50.0%)	
> 5 years	33 (66.0%)	17 (34.0%)	

Hemoglobin Levels: The mean hemoglobin level among the study participants was 11.5 ± 1.8 g/dL. The mean hemoglobin level was significantly lower in anemic patients (9.8 ± 1.2 g/dL) compared to non-anemic patients (13.4 ± 1.1 g/dL) ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Comparison of Hemoglobin Levels Between Anemic and Non-Anemic Patients

Group	Mean Hemoglobin (g/dL)	Standard Deviation	p-value
Anemic Patients (n=63)	9.8	1.2	<0.001
Non-Anemic Patients (n=57)	13.4	1.1	

Association of Anemia with Type and Duration of NCD: Anemia was more prevalent among patients with chronic kidney disease (66.7%),

followed by cardiovascular diseases (60.0%) and diabetes mellitus (57.1%). The prevalence of anemia also increased with the duration of NCD;

patients with a duration of NCD greater than 5 years had the highest prevalence of anemia (66.0%). Chi-square tests were used to assess the association between categorical variables. A statistically significant association was found between the presence of anemia and gender ($p = 0.015$), age group ($p = 0.026$), type of NCD ($p = 0.003$), and duration of NCD ($p < 0.001$). The association between hemoglobin levels and anemia status was also statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), as shown in Table 3.

Findings

- The overall prevalence of anemia among patients with non-communicable diseases at PMCH was 52.5%.
- Anemia was more prevalent among females, older age groups, and patients with chronic kidney disease.
- The mean hemoglobin level was significantly lower in anemic patients compared to non-anemic patients.
- The prevalence of anemia was positively associated with the duration of the NCD, with the highest prevalence observed in patients with a disease duration of more than 5 years.

Discussion

The results revealed that more than half of the participants (52.5%) were anemic, highlighting a significant burden of anemia in this population. The prevalence of anemia was notably higher in females (65.4%) compared to males (42.6%), indicating that gender plays a crucial role in the risk of developing anemia among patients with NCDs. This gender disparity may be influenced by factors such as nutritional deficiencies, hormonal differences, and other underlying health conditions more prevalent in women.

Age was also a significant factor, with older age groups showing a higher prevalence of anemia. Specifically, patients aged over 60 years had the highest prevalence of anemia at 70.0%. This finding suggests that aging may exacerbate the risk of anemia in individuals with chronic diseases, possibly due to declining physiological reserves, increased comorbidities, and the cumulative effects of long-term disease management.

The type of NCD was closely associated with anemia prevalence. Patients with (CKD) exhibited the highest prevalence of anemia (66.7%), followed by those with cardiovascular diseases (60.0%) and diabetes mellitus (57.1%). CKD is known to cause anemia through mechanisms such as reduced erythropoietin production, iron deficiency, and inflammation. Similarly, chronic conditions like diabetes and cardiovascular diseases may lead to

anemia due to factors like chronic inflammation, poor nutrition, and medication side effects.

Duration of disease emerged as another critical determinant, with patients who had been living with NCDs for more than five years showing a significantly higher prevalence of anemia (66.0%). This suggests that the longer a patient lives with an NCD, the greater the likelihood of developing anemia. The chronic nature of these diseases, combined with the long-term use of medications and the potential for cumulative organ damage, likely contributes to this increased risk.

Statistical analysis confirmed that the associations between anemia and gender, age, type of NCD, and duration of NCD were statistically significant. The mean hemoglobin level was significantly lower in anemic patients compared to non-anemic patients, reinforcing the need for early detection and management of anemia in this population .

Several investigations have revealed high rates and associated factors. A cross-sectional study in Eastern Ethiopia discovered that 64.8% of hospitalised patients were anaemic, and there were substantial connections between anaemia and chronic renal disease, chronic liver disease, and deep vein thrombosis. Furthermore, factors such as daily alcohol intake and malnutrition were highly associated with anaemia [9].

Similarly, a research in Northwestern Nigeria found that 42.9% of diabetic individuals were anaemic. The study found a weak but significant inverse association between haemoglobin concentration and variables such as age, duration of diabetes, and fasting blood sugar levels. Chronic renal disease and uncontrolled diabetes have been recognised as risk factors [10].

Additional evidence from Malaysia revealed that 35.3% of older persons were anaemic, with a higher frequency among those with diabetes, hypertension, and hypercholesterolaemia. The study found that advancing age and diabetes were reliable predictors of anaemia, particularly in people with disabilities such difficulties walking or self-care [11].

Conclusion

This study underscores the high prevalence of anemia among patients with NCDs, particularly among females, older adults, and those with CKD or long-standing disease. These findings highlight the importance of routine screening for anemia in patients with NCDs, along with tailored interventions to address this condition and improve overall patient outcomes.

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